

Molecular Dynamics Simulations Unveil the Aggregation Patterns and Salting out of Polyarginines at Zwitterionic POPC Bilayers in Solutions of Various Ionic Strength

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Table S1: The partial charges in the ProsECCo75 force field of charged groups in POPC lipid, R₉ side chain and termini, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, and Cl⁻ ions.

Scaled groups	POPC lipid		R ₉ peptide			ions		
	2O(PO ₄ ⁻)	choline	Gdm ⁺	-NH ₃ ⁺	-COO ⁻	Na ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Cl ⁻
Partial charges	-0.655	+0.75	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	+0.75	+1.50	-0.75

Table S2. The probability of adsorption of R₉ peptides at POPC, $n(\text{R}_9)_{\text{ad}}$, and R₉ aggregation events, together with the ratio of different group interactions is given in percentages in systems containing 6 R₉ peptides for the second set of MD simulations. Error bars were estimated by the standard deviation of three individual 500 ns MD simulation blocks.

system	$n(\text{R}_9)_{\text{ad}}$	Aggregation / %	Gdm ⁺ – Gdm ⁺ / %	Gdm ⁺ – COO ⁻ / %	NH ₃ ⁺ – COO ⁻ / %
Water	67.1±1.3	7.4±2.7	38.5±0.8	55.3±3.7	6.3±3.5
0.133 m NaCl	64.0±3.7	5.7±1.3	39.4±4.5	49.4±2.5	11.2±4.8
1.036 m NaCl	56.7±5.3	21.5±3.0	48.3±0.8	48.8±0.4	2.9±0.7
0.133 m CaCl₂	64.7±1.0	9.2±3.0	39.3±4.8	55.8±4.7	4.9±0.4
1.036 m CaCl₂	31.3±6.1	44.0±3.1	52.1±2.2	44.8±1.6	3.2±1.1

Table S3. The probability of adsorption of R₉ peptides at POPC, $n(\text{R}_9)_{\text{ad}}$, and R₉ aggregation events, together with the ratio of different group interactions is given in percentages in systems containing 16 R₉ peptides for the second set of MD simulations. Error bars were estimated by the standard deviation of three individual 500 ns MD simulation blocks.

system	$n(\text{R}_9)_{\text{ad}}$	Aggregation / %	Gdm ⁺ – Gdm ⁺ / %	Gdm ⁺ – COO ⁻ / %	NH ₃ ⁺ – COO ⁻ / %
Water	45.6±1.4	70.3±15.1	42.6±0.7	50.9±0.7	6.5±0.1
0.133 m NaCl	42.9±0.6	73.0±9.5	44.3±0.9	51.2±0.5	4.3±1.2
1.036 m NaCl	32.8±1.1	85.8±3.5	51.0±0.8	44.4±0.9	4.6±1.4
0.133 m CaCl₂	41.8±1.2	78.9±1.8	53.0±1.4	42.7±1.9	4.3±0.4
1.036 m CaCl₂	23.0±4.9	85.2±5.2	63.9±1.7	35.8±1.4	0.3±0.3

Table S4. The average lifetime of R₉ aggregates (in ps) of different sizes (dimer–heptamer and higher aggregates) at the POPC bilayer for low and high peptide concentrations in systems with different salt compositions and concentrations for the second set of MD simulations. The error bar is the standard deviation of the mean value when multiple aggregation events occur. The range of aggregate lifetimes is presented for larger aggregates (> heptamer).

system	dimer	trimer	tetramer	pentamer	hexamer	heptamer	> heptamer
Water	¹⁾ 1183 ± 350	400 ± 57	–	–	–	–	–
	²⁾ 876 ± 58	336 ± 33	268 ± 26	200 ± 39	217 ± 65	125 ± 25	–
0.133 m NaCl	566 ± 90	–	–	–	–	–	–
	670 ± 34	349 ± 22	271 ± 26	206 ± 31	150 ± 34	133 ± 33	–
1.065 m NaCl	836 ± 93	476 ± 90	150 ± 50	–	–	–	–
	621 ± 34	516 ± 31	303 ± 13	239 ± 15	254 ± 21	209 ± 39	100 – 200
0.133 m CaCl₂	684 ± 68	575 ± 217	–	–	–	–	–
	631 ± 31	444 ± 23	298 ± 25	287 ± 26	159 ± 18	226 ± 57	³⁾ ~100
1.065 m CaCl₂	1089 ± 133	795 ± 103	463 ± 67	217 ± 47	³⁾ ~200	–	–
	787 ± 60	596 ± 45	453 ± 33	416 ± 32	303 ± 20	249 ± 18	200 – 250

¹⁾ The upper row shows data for low peptide concentration.

²⁾ The lower row shows data for high peptide concentration.

³⁾ A single continuous aggregation event.

Fig. S1. Non-symmetrized number density profiles for peptide center of mass for low R_9 concentration (upper panel) and high R_9 concentrations (bottom panel) in different systems with respect to the distance from the POPC bilayer center for the original MD simulations. The number density of POPC phosphorus atoms is shown as the dashed line for the reference system without added salt for low and high peptide concentrations.

Fig. S2. Distance between the center of mass of 6 individual R₉ peptides (low peptide concentration) in the system with counterions only and the center of the POPC bilayer for the original MD simulations. For simplicity, the absolute distances (regardless of the bilayer leaflet) from the center of mass of the peptides to the POPC bilayer center are shown together. The first 500 ns were discarded from the analysis.

Fig. S3. Distance between the center of mass of 16 individual R₉ peptides (high peptide concentration) in the system with counterions only and the center of the POPC bilayer for the original MD simulations. For simplicity, the absolute distances (regardless of the bilayer leaflet) from the center of mass of the peptides to the POPC bilayer center are shown together. The first 500 ns were discarded from the analysis.

Fig. S4. Symmetrized number density profiles for peptide center of mass for low R_9 concentration (upper panel) and high R_9 concentrations (bottom panel) in different systems with respect to the distance from the POPC bilayer center for the second set of MD simulations. The number density of POPC phosphorus atoms is shown as the dashed line for the reference system without added salt for low and high peptide concentrations.

Fig. S5. Non-symmetrized number density profiles for peptide center of mass for low R_9 concentration (upper panel) and high R_9 concentrations (bottom panel) in different systems with respect to the distance from the POPC bilayer center for the second set of MD simulations. The number density of POPC phosphorus atoms is shown as the dashed line for the reference system without added salt for low and high peptide concentrations.

Fig. S6. Distance between the center of mass of 6 individual R₉ peptides (low peptide concentration) in the system with counterions only and the center of the POPC bilayer for the second set of MD simulations. For simplicity, the absolute distances (regardless of the bilayer leaflet) from the center of mass of the peptides to the POPC bilayer center are shown together. The first 500 ns were discarded from the analysis.

Fig. S7. Distance between the center of mass of 16 individual R₉ peptides (high peptide concentration) in the system with counterions only and the center of the POPC bilayer for the second set of MD simulations. For simplicity, the absolute distances (regardless of the bilayer leaflet) from the center of mass of the peptides to the POPC bilayer center are shown together. The first 500 ns were discarded from the analysis.

Aggregate types – low peptide concentration

Aggregate types – high peptide concentration

Fig. S8. The percentage of different-sized aggregates in systems with low peptide concentration (upper panel) and high peptide concentrations (bottom panel) in systems with different ionic strengths for the second set of MD simulations.

Fig S9. The maximum size of aggregates formed at the POPC membrane during simulation time for the second set of MD simulations. The first 500 ns were discarded from the analysis.